

Annexure

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1 Preliminary

1.1 NLP Techniques

The following NLP techniques are crucial for building the technical framework.

1.1.1 Pre-trained Language Model

A language model is a form of AI designed to understand and generate human language by learning patterns from data. Pre-trained language models (PLMs), a type of deep learning model, excel in various natural language processing tasks after training on extensive datasets. Notable for their state-of-the-art performance, these models, discussed in this section, operate on autoregressive prediction, optimizing text probability from left to right.

GPT-3: GPT-3 (1), an innovation by OpenAI, stands out as a leading language model renowned for its ability to generate human-like text that is both coherent and diverse. GPT-3 utilizes a hierarchy of transformer models, from 'Small' with 125 million parameters to '175B' with 175 billion parameters, showcasing a comprehensive understanding of language. Notably, this prowess demands substantial computational resources. Enter GPT-3.5 (2), the newer model equipped with a staggering 355 billion parameters, surpassing its predecessor. GPT-3.5 excels in enhancing precision and naturalness in responses, particularly beneficial for tasks such as language translation and text summarization.

ChatGPT, a specialized variant derived from GPT-3.5 (2), has been meticulously crafted for the purpose of generating text that is not only precise and detailed but also coherent, catering to various styles and objectives. The model underwent a refinement process involving fine-tuning, incorporating both supervised and reinforcement learning techniques. Notably, reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) took precedence in minimizing undesirable outputs, ensuring a more refined and positive user experience.

LLaMA: The LLaMA model (3), presented by Meta AI, comprises a suite of foundational language models ranging from 7B to 65B parameters, catering to various research needs within the AI community. Positioned as an advanced

foundational language model, LLaMA adopts an auto-regressive approach based on the transformer architecture, akin to models like GPT-3. Recently launched LLaMA-2 (4) model is the successor of LLaMA. Remarkably, LLaMA-2 achieves state-of-the-art performance while maintaining a 10% smaller size compared to GPT-3. Training on publicly available datasets containing 2 trillions of tokens ensures that LLaMA-2 is well-versed in a broad and diverse range of language constructs. Particularly noteworthy is the LLaMA-2-13B model, which outperforms GPT-3 across several benchmarks, underscoring its exceptional capabilities. Being a family of generative language model, LLaMA and LLaMA-2 models inherently possess the capacity to generate text. To leverage this capability for domain-specific NLP tasks, fine-tuning the LLaMA models on different datasets proves effective.

What sets LLaMA models apart from other Large Language Models (LLMs) is its lightweight and open-source quantized version. This unique feature enables convenient fine-tuning using standard GPUs like Nvidia A100, making it accessible even without GPU resources.

Mixtral 8x7B: Mixtral 8x7B (5) stands at the forefront of open-weight large language models (LLMs), leveraging a 46.7 billion parameter architecture and a cutting-edge Mixture of Experts (MoE) (6) design to redefine NLP capabilities. Its 8 expert sub-models per layer dynamically handle diverse linguistic features, achieving remarkable performance in text generation tasks. Mixtral 8x7B also has a larger context length of 32k tokens, which enables it to generate more coherent and relevant texts. Technical aspects of this LLM is summarized as follows:

1. *MoE Efficiency:* Unlike traditional LLMs, Mixtral’s sparsity reduces computational cost, achieving the performance of a 14-billion parameter model.
2. *Open Access:* Unfettered access to Mixtral’s parameters fosters transparency and community-driven research, paving the way for further optimization and customization.
3. *Text Generation Performance:* Mixtral establishes remarkable benchmarks, demonstrating exceptional performance in long-context tasks with perplexity scores as low as 3.06 (WikiText-2), a notable MBPP score of 60.7, an impressive GSM-8K score of 58.4, and an MT Bench score of 8.30. Notably, it surpasses both LLaMA-2 and GPT-3.5 in MBPP and GSM-8k scores.

1.1.2 Zero-shot Learning and Few-shot Learning

The presence of extensively annotated datasets on a large scale is imperative for the application of deep learning techniques. A notable hurdle emerges when conducting downstream tasks in domains where publicly available annotated datasets are limited. This challenge finds resolution through the innovative approaches of zero-shot and few-shot learning, as highlighted in relevant surveys (7; 8). According to (9), an approach to scaling up the recognition task by

developing such models capable of recognizing unseen classes without any prior training is called zero-shot learning. In traditional machine learning, models are trained on labeled examples of all classes they will encounter during testing. However, zero-shot learning tackles the challenge of classifying unseen classes by leveraging auxiliary information or attributes associated with the classes. On the other hand, the goal of few-shot learning is to recognize novel classes without performing rigorous training rather than introducing adaptability of the deep learning model using just a few illustrative examples (10). Few-shot learning algorithms aim to learn from these limited examples by leveraging the similarities and relationships between classes. They typically use transfer learning techniques or employ meta-learning approaches to learn how to quickly adapt to new classes or tasks with limited data.

1.1.3 Template Based Prompt Engineering

One of the latest approaches to achieve zero-shot learning is prompt-based learning which involves developing templates for specific NLP tasks. The process of building prompting functions or templates depending upon the input text data and the specific task is called prompt engineering. Traditional supervised learning trains a model to take an input $\mathbf{x}$ and predict an output $\mathbf{y}$ denoted as $P(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x})$. On the other hand, prompt-based learning is based on language models that model the probability of text directly (7). The template is developed on top of the original text $\mathbf{x}$ and usually, the template has some unfilled slots. The language model performs the prediction tasks based on the template. It predicts the text for the unfilled slots and generates the string $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$. The final output $\mathbf{y}$ is then derived from $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$.

Table 1: Notations and steps involved in prompt learning.

Name	Notation	Example	Explanation
Input	$\mathbf{x}$	On clicking privacy policy link, a window must appear.	Input text
Output	$\mathbf{y}$	GUI	Output label
Possible Labels	$\mathbf{z}$	{Event, GUI, Hardware, Platform, Organization, ...}	Set of labels from which the output will be decided.
Prompt Function	$f_{prompt}(x)$	[X1]. The entity type of the word [X2] is [Z]	A function creates a template from input and adds a slot Z that will be filled later.
Prompt	$\hat{x}$	On clicking privacy policy link, a window must appear. The entity type of the word window is [Z]	The modified text where [X] is filled but [Z] is not.
Filled Prompt	$f_{fill}(\hat{x}, z^*)$	On clicking privacy policy link, a window must appear. The entity type of the word window is Event	[Z] can be filled with any answer.
Answer Prompt	$f_{fill}(\hat{x}, z)$	On clicking privacy policy link, a window must appear. The entity type of the word window is GUI	[Z] is filled with true answer.

1.1.4 Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)

Large language models (LLMs) have revolutionized natural language processing, exhibiting remarkable capabilities in text generation. However, their outputs can be factually inconsistent and lack grounding in real-world knowledge. Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) (11) is an approach that empowers LLMs by leveraging external data sources to improve the accuracy, reliability,

and context-awareness of their generated responses. RAG bridges this gap by seamlessly integrating external knowledge retrieval with LLM generation. It operates in three key stages:

1. *Prompt Analysis*: The LLM analyzes the user’s prompt and extracts key information points, entities, and relations.
2. *Document Retrieval*: Utilizing the extracted information, RAG searches a pre-defined external knowledge source (e.g., document repository, database, API) for relevant documents. Semantic retrieval techniques ensure retrieved documents are highly pertinent to the prompt’s context.
3. *Augmented Generation*: The retrieved documents are then processed by the LLM to enrich its understanding of the prompt. Key facts, entity relationships, and document sentiment are extracted and integrated into the LLM’s internal representation. This augmented knowledge informs the final generation process, leading to more accurate, reliable, and contextually-aware outputs.

1.1.5 Vector Database and Vector Search

A Vector Database (12) comprises a compilation of high-dimensional vectors that represent diverse entities and concepts. Each vector corresponds to a specific feature or attribute of the entity, denoted by a numeric value. These databases facilitate the efficient retrieval and comparison of similar entities based on their distinctive features or attributes. Widely applied in domains such as image and audio search, recommendation systems, and anomaly detection, Vector Databases stand out for their dual functionality, combining traditional database capabilities with the capacity to search and compare vectors within an index.

Vector Search (13) involves the process of identifying the most similar vector in a database to a given query vector. This typically entails calculating the cosine similarity between the query vector and the vectors stored in the database. The cosine similarity metric gauges the angle between the two vectors and is widely recognized for its effectiveness in measuring vector similarity. With vector search, users gain the ability to search for objects without the need for specific keywords or metadata classifications. Moreover, it extends its utility by providing a broader spectrum of results, unveiling matches that are similar or proximate and potentially revealing hidden items that might otherwise go unnoticed.

1.2 Risk Categorisation

The following figure shows the categorization of risk impact, probability and total risk in different regions.

		Impact					Risk Exposure
		Low	Moderate	Significant	Major	High/ Catastrophic	
		0-0.2	>0.2-0.4	>0.4-0.6	>0.6-0.8	>0.8-1.0	
Probability	High	>0.8-1.0	MODERATE	SIGNIFICANT	HIGH	HIGH	
	Major	>0.6-0.8	MODERATE	SIGNIFICANT	HIGH	HIGH	
	Significant	>0.4-0.6	LOW	MODERATE	SIGNIFICANT	HIGH	
	Moderate	>0.2-0.4	LOW	MODERATE	SIGNIFICANT	SIGNIFICANT	
	Low	0-0.2	LOW	LOW	MODERATE	MODERATE	

Figure 1: Risk Categorization

2 Algorithms

Algorithm 1 Risk Exposure

Arguments:

1. C_R : A set of change requests.
2. $G_R = \{V, E\}$: G is an RIG where V comprises of both FR and NFR and $E = E_{FF} \cup E_{FN} \cup E_{NN}$

Output:

1. L_{ff} : A list of FR-FR propagation chains.
2. L_{fn} : A list of FR-NFR propagation chains.
3. L_{nn} : A list of NFR-NFR propagation chains.

```

1: function RISK_EXPOSURE( $C_R, G$ )
2:    $cat =$  DETERMINE_SCENARIO( $C_R$ )
3:   if  $cat == "SC - 1" \vee cat == "SC - 3"$  then
4:      $L_{ff} =$  PROP_FF( $C_R, E_{FF}$ )
5:      $L_{fn} =$  PROP_FN( $C_R, E_{FN}, L_{ff}$ )
6:      $L_{nn} =$  PROP_NN( $C_R, E_{NN}, L_{fn}$ )
7:   else
8:      $L_{fn} =$  PROP_FN( $C_R, E_{FN}, empty$ )
9:      $L_{nn} =$  PROP_NN( $C_R, E_{NN}, empty$ )
10:  end if
11:   $L_{ff}, L_{fn}, L_{nn} =$  REMOVE_REDUNDANCY( $L_{ff}, L_{fn}, L_{nn}$ )
12: end function

```

Algorithm 2 PROP_{FF}

```
1: function PROPFF(CR, EFF)
2:   Let size = 0.
3:   for each req ∈ CR do
4:     for each eij in EFF do
5:       if eij contains req ∧ eij.value > β then
6:         Set eij.prob = eij.value / max    ▷ max is the maximum
dependency value
7:         Insert node eij to Lff[size].
8:         size++
9:       end if
10:    end for
11:    while TRUE do
12:      for i = 0 to size do
13:        Let emp = ⟨ fm, fp ⟩ be the last edge in Lff[i]
14:        Find edge epk = ⟨ fp, fk ⟩ in EFF .
15:        prob = emp.prob * epk.value
16:        if prob ≥ β then
17:          Set epk.prob = prob
18:          Insert node epk to Lff[i].
19:        end if
20:      end for
21:    end while
22:  end for
23:  Return Lff
24: end function
```

Algorithm 3 PROP_{FN}

```
1: function PROPFN(CR, EFN, Lff)
2:   for each req ∈ CR ∨ fri ∈ Lff do ‘
3:     for each ejk = ⟨ fj, nfk ⟩ in EFN do
4:       if ejk contains req ∨ fri ∈ ejk then
5:         if ejk.value ≥ β then
6:           Insert ejk to Lfn.
7:         end if
8:       end if
9:     end for
10:  end for
11:  Return Lfn
12: end function
```

3 Results

3.1 Evaluation of Project ID: 33

Project ID 33 consists of 9 FRs, and 2 NFRs and has a total of 16 different interactions (dependency and conflicts) among the requirements. There 4 modified

Algorithm 4 PROP_{NN}

```
1: function PROPNN(CR, ENN, Lfn) ‘
2:   for each ejk = ⟨ fj, nfk ⟩ ∈ Lfn do
3:     for each emp = ⟨ nfm, nfp ⟩ in ENN do
4:       if nfk ∈ emp ∧ emp.value ≥ β then
5:         Insert emp to Lnn.
6:       end if
7:     end for
8:   end for
9:   Return Lnn
10: end function
```

Algorithm 5 Risk Measurement

Arguments:

1. *cat*: Scenario type
2. *L_{ff}*: FR-FR propagation chains.
3. *L_{fn}*: FR-NFR propagation chains.
4. *L_{nn}*: NFR-NFR propagation chains.

Output: *Risk_{val}*: A measure of risk.

```
1: function RISK_MEASUREMENT(Type, Lff, Lfn, Lnn)
2:   if cat == "SC - 1" ∨ cat == "SC - 3" then
3:     Iff = IMPACTFF(Lff)
4:     Ifn = FNFIMPACT(Lfn)
5:     Inn = NFNFIMPACT(Lnn)
6:     I = Iff + Ifn + Inn
7:   else
8:     Ifn = FNFIMPACT(Lfn)
9:     Inn = NFNFIMPACT(Lnn)
10:    I = Ifn + Inn
11:   end if
12:   P = PROBABILITY(Lff, Lfn, Lnn)
13:   Riskval = P * I
14: end function
```

requirements (2 FR and 2 NFR).

The *Risk Exposure* module generated 9 different propagation chains. Figure 2(a) shows the risk exposure graph. We have represented the requirements in the *CARO_v2* tool through labels. The pink-colored nodes in the graph are the ones that are modified. The dark red colored nodes are the ones that are affected due to this change. There is only one FR-FR propagation chain ⟨fr8, fr9⟩. As fr9 is the only requirement that is directly dependent on fr8. The

Algorithm 6 FFImpact

```
1: function FFIMPACT( $L_{ff}$ )
2:   Initialize array  $FRpair[]$  as empty.
3:   Initialize  $\Delta_{ff} = 0, W_{ff} = 0$ 
4:   for each  $e_{ik} = \langle fr_i, fr_k \rangle \in L_{ff}$  do
5:     if  $e_{ik} \notin FRpair$  then
6:       Add  $e_{ik}$  to  $FRpair$ 
7:        $\Delta_{ff} = \Delta_{ff} + e_{ik}.value$ 
8:       if  $e_{ik}.value >= 1 \wedge e_{ik}.value <= 35$  then
9:          $cat = 1$ 
10:      else if  $e_{ik}.value > 35 \wedge e_{ik}.value <= 70$  then
11:         $cat = 2$ 
12:      else if  $e_{ik}.value > 70$  then
13:         $cat = 3$ 
14:      end if
15:      if  $e_{ik}.type$  is "Cohesion" then
16:         $type = 1$ 
17:      else
18:         $type = 2$ 
19:      end if
20:      if  $fr_i$  is frozen  $\vee fr_k$  is frozen then
21:         $frozen = 1$ 
22:      end if
23:       $W_{ff} = cat + type + frozen$ 
24:    end if
25:  end for
26:   $W_{ff} = W_{ff} / (6 * SIZE(FRpair))$ 
27:   $I_{ff} = \Delta_{ff} * W_{ff}$ 
28:  Return  $I_{ff}$ 
29: end function
```

other affected FRs are due to their interdependence with the modified NFRs.

Figure 2(b) shows the risk measurement values. It also gives the impact value of each chain. We can observe that although there are more FR-NFR chains than FR-FR chains, the FR-FR chain holds a greater impact on the risk value. This is due to the high dependency between **fr8**, **fr9** and also their type of association.

Figure 2(c) shows the strategy for minimizing the impact of change requests. It provides an order for handling the requirements. At first, it gives an optimal order considering the RIG. Then it provides different other alternate options considering risk category. In this case, we have two alternate options available where the orders among **fr3**, **fr2**, and **fr1**, **fr3** are changed.

Algorithm 7 FNFImpact

```
1: function FNIMPACT( $L_{fnf}$ )
2:   Initialize  $\Delta_{fn} = 0, W_{fn} = 0$ 
3:   for each  $e_{ik} = \langle fr_i, nfr_k \rangle \in L_{fn}$  do
4:      $S = e_{ik}.satisfaction, P = e_{ik}.priority$ 
5:     if  $S > 0 \wedge S \leq 35$  then
6:        $sat = 3$ 
7:     else if  $S > 35 \wedge S \leq 70$  then
8:        $sat = 2$ 
9:     else if  $S > 70$  then
10:       $sat = 1$ 
11:    end if
12:    if  $P > 1 \wedge priority \leq 35$  then
13:       $prio = 1$ 
14:    else if  $P > 35 \wedge P < 70$  then
15:       $prio = 2$ 
16:    else if  $P \geq 75$  then
17:       $prio = 3$ 
18:    end if
19:     $W_{fn} = W_{fn} + S + P$ 
20:  end for
21:   $W_{fn} = W_{fn} / (6 * \text{SIZE}(L_{fn}))$ 
22:   $I_{fn} = \Delta_{fn} * W_{fn}$ 
23:  Return  $I_{fnf}$ 
24: end function
```

3.2 CARO _ Tool result comparison with LLM Results

We have compared our risk assessment result with the results generated by LLMs. Table 2 shows the comparison of the results. This comparison is done with 6 PROMISE projects.

4 Prompts Used in the Framework

4.1 Prompt for Conflict Analysis Among Requirements

In the proposed framework, we provide the following prompt to the AI agent to analyze the requirements specifications thoroughly to identifies the conflict among the requirements.

You are an AI assistant for requirements analysis, You will help to identify potential conflicts among the following requirements specifications.

[requirements specifications]

Analyze these requirements from the perspective of a expert requirements engineer. Based on your understanding of different types of requirements and

Algorithm 8 NNImpact

```
1: function NFNIMPACT( $L_{nn}$ )
2:   Initialize  $\Delta_{nn} = 0, W_{nn} = 0$ 
3:   for each  $e_{ik} = \langle nfr_i, nfr_k \rangle \in L_{nn}$  do
4:      $P_i = nfr_i.priority, P_k = nfr_k.priority$ 
5:     if  $P_i > 0 \wedge P_i \leq 35$  then
6:        $prio1 = 1$ 
7:     else if  $P_i > 35 \wedge P_i \leq 70$  then
8:        $prio1 = 2$ 
9:     else if  $P_i > 70$  then
10:       $prio1 = 3$ 
11:     end if
12:     if  $P_k > 0 \wedge P_k \leq 35$  then
13:        $prio2 = 1$ 
14:     else if  $P_k > 35 \wedge P_k \leq 70$  then
15:        $prio2 = 2$ 
16:     else if  $P_k > 70$  then
17:        $prio2 = 3$ 
18:     end if
19:      $W_{nn} = W_{nn} + prio1 + prio2$ 
20:   end for
21:    $W_{nn} = W_{nn} / (6 * 2 * \text{SIZE}(L_{nn}))$ 
22:    $I_{nn} = \Delta_{nn} * W_{nn}$ 
23:   Return  $I_{nn}$ 
24: end function
```

potential interaction points, you will be looking for conflicts across the following categories:

Operational Conflict: Clashing behaviours, conditions, or performance goals. Data Conflict: Inconsistency in data handling, processing, or access. User Interaction Conflict: Conflicting needs or expectations in user interface and interaction design. Timing Conflict: Clashes in scheduling, response times, or availability requirements. Security and Compliance Conflict: Conflicting security requirements or compliance standards. Technical Compatibility Conflict: Incompatibility with existing systems or software infrastructure.

For each identified conflict, provide the following information in a CSV format:

Requirement 1, Requirement 2, Type of Conflict, Conflict Score (1-10, with 10 being the highest), Reason for Conflict

4.2 Prompt for Dependency Analysis Among Requirements

In order to analyze the dependencies among the requirements specifications, we specifically provide the following prompt to the AI agent.

Table 2: Comparison of CARO_v2 results with LLMs

PROMISE PROJECT ID	MODIFIED REQUIREMENT ID	RISK EXPOSURE		
		CARO_V2 TOOL RESULT	GPT-4 RESULT	MIXTRAL RESULT
1	nfr4	nfr1, fr11, fr12, fr15, fr17	nfr1, fr19, fr21, fr18,	nfr1
	fr19	fr2, fr3, fr10, nfr2, nfr3, nfr6, nfr7	N/A	fr10
2	nfr5	fr11, nfr6, nfr28, nfr6	nfr6, nfr28	N/A
	nfr6	fr1, nfr27, nfr5	nfr27	N/A
	nfr17	fr5, nfr14, nfr26	nfr14	nfr14, nfr18
	nfr21	fr3, nfr22, nfr23	nfr22, nfr23	N/A
	nfr28	fr3, fr6, nfr27	nfr27	N/A
	fr11	nfr9, nfr5, nfr7, nfr20, nfr26	nfr9	nfr9, fr1
nfr27	fr3, fr9, nfr6, nfr7, nfr8, nfr5	N/A	nfr6, nfr7, nfr8	
3	fr1	fr2, fr3, nfr2, nfr5, nfr7, nfr11, nfr12, nfr15, nfr30	fr3, fr5, fr10, fr8, fr20, fr42	N/A
	nfr2	fr1, fr2, fr3, nfr6, nfr5, nfr7	nfr6	nfr5, nfr7
	nfr3	fr10, fr15, fr19, nfr4, nfr3, nfr1	nfr4	nfr3, nfr1
	nfr5	fr1, fr3, fr10, nfr6, nfr7, nfr8	N/A	nfr8
	nfr7	fr9, fr12, fr23, fr31, fr32, nfr5, nfr8	N/A	nfr5
	nfr15	fr10, nfr12	nfr12	N/A
	nfr16	fr8, fr25, nfr18	nfr19	N/A
nfr20	fr15, nfr21, nfr23	nfr23	N/A	
4	nfr20	fr22, nfr19	nfr19	N/A
5	fr1	fr6, fr2, fr10, nfr6, nfr11, nfr12	fr6	N/A
	fr7	fr8, nfr4, nfr9	fr8	N/A
	fr27	fr28, nfr4, nfr5	fr28	N/A
	fr31	fr32, fr34, nfr8, nfr29	fr32	fr34
	fr34	fr35, nfr6, nfr9	fr35	fr35
	nfr1	fr35, fr36, nfr6, nfr2	nfr6	N/A
nfr3	fr12, nfr14, nfr20	nfr20	nfr14	
6	nfr1	nfr5, nfr25, fr11	nfr3, nfr25	nfr25
	nfr17	nfr18, nfr19, fr24	nfr18, nfr19	nfr18
	nfr4	nfr47, nfr26, fr26	NF	nfr26
	nfr36	nfr46, nfr35	NF	nfr46
	nfr47	nfr4, nfr22, nfr2, nfr38, fr1	NF	nfr38

- *Enhanced Task Relevance:* By simulating the perspective of a specific role (e.g., requirements engineer, journalist, marketing expert), the prompt directs the LLM to prioritize information and reasoning relevant to that role. This leads to more tailored and valuable responses for the intended audience.
- *Creative Exploration and Style:* Incorporating personas can open up avenues for more creative and stylistic outputs. Different roles may have distinct communication styles, preferred information sources, or biases, which the LLM can mimic to generate outputs that feel authentic and engaging.
- *Efficient Communication and Understanding:* Using personas can lead to more concise and focused prompts, as the LLM doesn't need to be explicitly informed about certain background knowledge or goals. This improves communication efficiency and reduces the risk of misunderstandings.

4.3 Experimental Evaluation of Dependency Extractor

In this section, we analyze dependency scores from three Language Models (LLMs) applied to software requirements specifications. Our aim is to evalu-

ate how well these scores align with the 68-95-99.7 rule (14), providing insights into the distribution of conflicts identified by the LLMs. We utilize bell curves (PDFs) for each set of scores and plot z-scores to quantify individual deviations from the mean.

Figure 3: Distribution of Z-scores Across Different Standard Deviations

Bell Curves and Rule Adherence:

The bell curves provide insights into conflict score distributions from different LLMs. 68-95-99.7 summarizes the followings (Considering μ is the mean and σ is the standard deviation.):

- *68% Rule:* Approximately 68% of scores fall within one standard deviation. ($\mu \pm \sigma$)
- *95% Rule:* Nearly 95% fall within two standard deviations. ($\mu \pm 2\sigma$)
- *99.7% Rule:* A high concentration (99.7%) is within three standard deviations, closely adhering to the rule. ($\mu \pm 3\sigma$)

Z-Score Analysis for Dependency Scores

To further quantify the distribution characteristics, we analyze the z-scores for each individual dependency score. Z-scores represent the number of standard deviations of a dependency score is from the mean, providing a quantitative measure of deviation.

Interpretation: A z-score of 1 corresponds to one standard deviation above the mean, -1 to one standard deviation below, and so forth. The z-score plot reveals how closely individual conflict scores align with the expected distribution.

Observations: The analysis of the z-scores in relation to the 68-95-99.7 rule (also known as the empirical rule) has yielded the following results:

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the z-scores, the data shows that approximately 89.22% of the z-scores fall within ($\mu \pm \sigma$), which is much higher than the empirical rule’s 68%. 97.15% fall within ($\mu \pm 2\sigma$), which is satisfying 95%

expectation by the rule and 100% fall within $(\mu \pm 3\sigma)$ which again satisfies 99% expectation.

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